

Article

Investigating How Policies and Other Conditions Contribute to Influencing Agricultural GHG Emissions in the EU

Francesco Galioto *

CREA Research Centre for Agricultural Policies and Bioeconomy, 00187 Rome, Italy; irene.criscuoli@crea.gov.it (I.C.); andrea.martelli@crea.gov.it (A.M.); mvalentina.lasorella@crea.gov.it (M.V.L.); ilaria.falconi@crea.gov.it (I.F.); danilo.marandola@crea.gov.it (D.M.); giovanni.daraguccione@crea.gov.it (G.D.G.); francesca.varia@crea.gov.it (F.V.)

* Correspondence: francesco.galioto@crea.gov.it; Tel.: +39-3403758484

Abstract: The present study aims at investigating the potential impacts of agricultural policies on GHG emissions from agriculture across the European Union. The study begins by providing evidence on how the key CAP reforms contributed to the structural changes the European agriculture faced in the past. Based on these facts, we introduce the context of implementation of the 2014–2022 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), within which many interventions were designed to improve sustainability and increase competitiveness, and we formulate hypotheses on how CAP instruments can contribute differently to influencing GHG emissions from agriculture. The hypotheses formulated concern the following: (1) the influence of the income support payment on land prices and, consequently, on land distribution between small and large landowners; (2) the influence of the coupled payment on agricultural specialization; (3) the influence of agri-environmental-climate measures on the sustainable management of agricultural lands. These causalities can have direct and indirect effects on GHG emissions from agriculture. The method of qualitative comparative analysis (QCA) is used to investigate the above-mentioned causalities and to cluster observations based on similar combinations of conditions (i.e., drivers) and outcomes (i.e., positive or negative variations in GHG emissions from agriculture between the end and the beginning of the CAP programming period). The results reveal that the increase in GHG emissions from agriculture over the study period is mainly attributable to the low share of agricultural land under management contracts targeting climate change mitigation and carbon sequestration through the CAP. CAP payments coupled with production were found to contribute to further increasing GHG emissions from agriculture in some eastern and northern EU countries. Livestock concentrations, income support payments and the high price of agricultural land drive the increase in GHG emissions for other central and eastern EU countries. The paper concludes by addressing existing shortcomings due to conflicting interventions in the current CAP strategic plans.

Citation: Galioto, F.; Criscuoli, I.; Martelli, A.; Lasorella, M.V.; Falconi, I.; Marandola, D.; Dara Guccione, G.; Varia, F. Investigating How Policies and Other Conditions Contribute to Influencing Agricultural GHG Emissions in the EU. *Land* **2024**, *13*, 1745. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land13111745>

Academic Editor: Xin Zhao

Received: 30 August 2024

Revised: 10 October 2024

Accepted: 19 October 2024

Published: 24 October 2024

Keywords: qualitative comparative analysis; policy evaluation; climate change mitigation; soil health; rural development programs

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Agriculture contributes to global warming [1]. Intensification of crop and livestock production and unsustainable soil management have been identified as the main drivers of increasing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from agriculture [2,3]. The increasing concentration of livestock in some regions and the increasing specialization of farming systems exert severe pressure on the environment [4]. Agricultural intensification (e.g., growing the same crop year after year, deep tillage techniques, excessive use of chemical inputs) degrades soils [5] and increases the risk of diseases and pest outbreaks¹. This implies the use of larger amounts of fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides [5], with direct impacts on GHG emissions [10], pollution and biodiversity loss [11].

Nevertheless, reducing GHG emissions from agriculture is possible. Such a reduction can be pursued by the territorial reconfiguration of farming systems towards greater integration between agriculture and livestock [4].

Variations in agricultural GHG emissions reflect changes in cropping and livestock systems and production methods, and these changes are likely to be influenced by various drivers, including policies [12].

The aim of this study is to investigate variations in agricultural GHG emissions in the European Union (EU) during the 2014–2022 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) programming period and the causes behind them.

In the EU, GHG emissions from agriculture are estimated annually by national environment agencies² by combining information on crop and livestock typologies, fertilizer management, crop residue management, livestock and manure management and other sources of agricultural GHG emissions³.

According to the European Environment Agency (EEA) [14], the EU has reduced its net GHG emissions by 31% compared to 1990. Energy supply and energy-intensive industries are the sectors that mostly contributed to this reduction.

GHG emissions from the agricultural sector represent about 10% of the total EU emissions [15,16], and they have decreased by 3% between 2005 and 2021, while a more pronounced reduction was observed between 1990 and 2005 (−20%). There are large differences in the variations of GHG emissions between member states (MSs) with reference to the 2014–2022 CAP programming period (Figure 1). At the end of the programming period, emissions increased by more than 10% in Cyprus, Hungary and Bulgaria, while they decreased by more than 10% in Greece [16]; these reductions were mainly associated with the loss of competitiveness of farms (e.g., a reduction in the number of dairy cows).

Figure 1. Variations in GHG emissions from agriculture (2022–2014% var). Source: our elaboration on Eurostat [12]. Notes: Since the entry into force of the Withdrawal Agreement that established the UK’s exit from the EU (on 31 January 2020 at midnight CET), the UK must be considered as a third country. However, it has been included for the purposes of this research. CY—Cyprus; HU—Hungary; BG—Bulgaria; SL—Slovenia; IE—Ireland; CZ—Czech Republic; PL—Poland; LU—Luxemburg; SE—Sweden; DK—Denmark; HR—Croatia; FI—Finland; MT—Malta; RO—Romania; AT—Austria; LV—Latvia; PT—Portugal; BE—Belgium; NL—Netherlands; FR—France; EE—Estonia; ES—Spain; IT—Italy; UK—United Kingdom; DE—Germany; LT—Lithuania; SK—Slovakia; EL—Greece.

Against this background, there has been much debate about whether the climate-friendly farming practices supported by the CAP have failed to deliver the desired results, at least in terms of climate change commitments to reduce GHG emissions [16]. Some researchers have attributed this failure to the fact that the CAP, through its various reforms, has essentially continued to favor the intensification of EU farming systems [17,18].

For example, the sudden decline in agricultural land in Europe in the early 1990s is thought to be linked to the Mac Sharry CAP reform, considered the first real CAP reform

since its inception⁴, which introduced payments linked to production (coupled payments) instead of price supports [19].

Coupled payments contributed to favoring the gradual abandonment of marginal agricultural land [20] and the concentration of agriculture in the most productive areas. Subsequently, the decoupling of subsidies from production and the introduction of area-based payments to compensate farmers for certain environmental commitments (cross-compliance), introduced in 2003 with the Fischler CAP reform, contributed to pushing up land prices [21,22], forcing small farmers out of business and discouraging new entrants [12]. This phenomenon occurred especially in some Mediterranean [23] and eastern countries [24] that joined the EU between 2004 and 2007 [25,26].

These facts support the hypothesis of a causal relationship between agricultural policies, land markets and structural trends in the agricultural sector. Based on this evidence, it looks reasonable and highly relevant to assess whether and how the latest CAP programming period (2014–2022) has contributed to the observed trends in GHG emissions from agriculture and to the achievement of the EU priority “Promoting resource efficiency and supporting the shift towards a low carbon and climate resilient economy in agriculture, food and forestry sectors, with a focus on the following areas: (. . .) (d) reducing greenhouse gas and ammonia emissions from agriculture; (e) fostering carbon conservation and sequestration in agriculture and forestry” (art. 6. Reg. EU 2021/2115)⁵.

To this end, we used country-level information and performed a qualitative comparative analysis (QCA) in order to provide empirical evidence to confirm or reject the study’s hypotheses.

In the following, we describe the method and data used for the analysis, the results obtained, discuss the findings in light of the theoretical expectations, make some concluding remarks addressing shortcomings of the current CAP National Strategic Plans, as well as outline limitations of the approach used in this study and some ideas for further research on the topic.

2. Data and Methods

In the present section, we describe the methodological approach used to examine some of the conditions that are thought to influence the MSs’ GHG emissions, the data we used for the analysis and the indexing procedure we implemented.

2.1. The QCA Method

The QCA method allows identification of necessary and sufficient conditions (i.e., causes) for an outcome (i.e., effect) [27]. A condition is commonly defined as necessary if this must be present for a certain outcome to occur, but the condition might be present even in the absence of the outcome. A condition is defined as sufficient if its presence implies the presence of a certain outcome, but the outcome can occur even in the absence of the condition (i.e., the outcome can be explained also by other conditions) [28].

A combination of conditions can influence the outcome and its absence. There are three common Boolean operations in QCA: negation (the non-occurrence of the condition/outcome), logical AND (Boolean multiplication) and logical OR (Boolean addition). Here, we use the following notations: \sim for negation, $*$ for multiplication (the Boolean multiplication implies the presence of both conditions), $+$ for addition (the Boolean addition implies the presence of one of the conditions).

Consistency and the coverage parameters of fit, ranging from 0 to 1, allow us to verify the existence of necessary and sufficient conditions for an outcome to occur.

Consistency is the degree to which the empirical evidence is in line with the statement of necessity or sufficiency. For necessity, imperfect consistency (below the ideal score of 1) is determined when the condition is not present every time the outcome occurs. For sufficiency, imperfect consistency is determined when the outcome does not occur every time the condition is present.

Coverage is the empirical importance of results. For sufficiency, the coverage corresponds to the share of the outcome associated with the occurrence of the condition (i.e., how much of the outcome is explained by the condition). For necessity, the coverage corresponds to the share of the negated outcome (i.e., non-occurrence of the outcome) associated with the non-occurrence of the condition (i.e., how much of the negated outcome is not explained by the condition). As for consistency, scores less than 1 indicate imperfect relationships.

Consistency is the most crucial measure, as it reports the strength of the causal relationship between conditions and outcomes. The standard necessity consistency threshold is 0.9, which permits a small degree of inconsistency to accommodate measurement error and imperfect relationships. The standard sufficiency consistency threshold is 0.75, which indicates that a given condition (or combination of conditions) is generally sufficient to produce the outcome [29–31]. The standard coverage score threshold is 0.6 for necessity and nil for sufficiency.

In QCA, the analysis of sufficiency follows the analysis of necessity, and the analysis of the negated outcome follows the analysis of the outcome. The analysis of sufficiency allows obtaining different solutions that lay between two endpoints of possible results: the conservative solution and the parsimonious solution. The conservative solution is the solution that privileges complexity and is based on observed combinations of conditions. The parsimonious solution allows simplifying the complex solution by including logical reminders in the minimization process. The logical reminders are combinations of conditions not observed in the group of observations. An intermediate solution is obtained by avoiding the inclusion of implausible logical reminders, and it allows highlighting relevant differences on causal relations. Logical reminders are implausible when they contradict the underlying expectations. Underline expectations are defined directional expectations in QCA because they drive selection of the logical reminders used to simplify the solution of the algorithm. Appendix A provides further details on how we handled logical reminders to search the intermediate solution.

It is worth noting that in this section we described the general procedure we followed to run QCA by providing the terminology and concepts we used to enable the interpretation of the results. For a more detailed description of the methodology, we recommend reading [30,31]. The analysis was carried out using the QCA package of R developed by [32].

2.2. Definitions of Thresholds and Directional Expectations

Table 1 provides information on the factors that are thought to influence changes in agricultural GHG emissions and that were used to carry out the QCA. There are one outcome and ten conditions. The outcome set is calculated based on the ‘2014–2022 change in GHG emissions’, which is annually reported by MSs to the EEA (see Section 1 for more details). The occurrence of a GHG outcome represents an increase in emissions over the observation period, while its negation (i.e., the non-occurrence of a GHG outcome) represents a decrease in emissions. The ten conditions refer to structural changes, policy interventions or land market prices. Information on structural changes and land market prices is obtained from Eurostat (see Table 1 for the reference sources), while information on policy interventions is obtained from Agridata (Table 1) and comes from the national reports on the implementation of the CAP, which are annually submitted by the MSs to the European Commission.

The structural changes concern the 2014–2022 variations in the utilized agricultural areas (from which we derive the UAA condition) and in the number of livestock units (from which we derive the LVK condition), the variation in the number of farms larger than 100 ha UAA (from which we derive the LANDSP condition) and in the number of livestock farms larger than 300 LSU (from which we derive the LVKSP condition). The occurrence of the conditions described above refers to a positive variation over the observation period, while their negation a negative variation.

Table 1. Measurement and calibration.

Type of Set	Set	Description	Calibration ³ (Set Membership)			Source
			Fully Out	Neither In or Out	Fully In	
			0.05	0.5	0.95	
Outcome	GHG	2022–2014 variation in GHG emissions from agriculture (% var).	−0.080	0.000	0.030	European Environment Agency. Data source: https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/ (accessed on 12 November 2023)
	LAND	2022–2014 UAA variation of farms with a size larger than 100 ha (% var).	−0.100	0.008	0.120	Eurostat. Data source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/ (accessed on 12 November 2023)
Structural changes	LVK	2022–2014 size variation of livestock farms larger than 300 LSU ² (% var).	−0.080	0.000	0.100	
	LANDSP	2022–2014 UAA variation of farms with a size larger than 100 ha (% var).	−0.100	0.000	0.150	
	LVKSP	2022–2014 size variation of livestock farms larger than 300 LSU (% var).	−0.100	0.000	0.130	
Conditions	SAPS	Countries for which the basic payment scheme (BPS) is based on the eligible hectares declared by farmers and where the level is the same for all hectares in the country (0–1).	0.000	0.500	1.000	Declarations of expenditure for the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development. Data source: https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/ (accessed on 12 November 2023)
	BASIC	Income support fund ratio on the total 2014–2022 CAP funding (%).	0.400	0.520	0.600	Annual implementation reports of Rural Development programs. Data source: https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/ (accessed on 12 November 2023)
	FUNDVCS	Funds ratio addressed to coupled payments on the total 2014–2022 CAP funding (%).	0.032	0.075	0.100	
	LANDCSQ	Percentage of agricultural and forest land under management contracts contributing to carbon sequestration, focus area 5E ¹ (% on the UAA).	0.050	0.200	2.000	
	LANDGHG	Percentage of agricultural land under management contracts targeting reduction in GHG and/or ammonia emissions, focus area 5D ¹ (% on the UAA).	0.005	1.000	8.000	
Land market	LANDPRICE	2022–2014 average sales prices of agricultural lands (euro/ha of UAA).	10,000	15,000	25,000	Eurostat. Data source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/ (accessed on 12 November 2023)

Notes: ¹ Focus areas 5E and 5D—The hectares of agricultural land and forestry area under management contracts targeting environmental and climate action within these focus areas are reported by MSs to the European Commission in the Annual Implementation Reports (AIR) of rural development programs. Investments in physical assets to reduce emissions and subsidies to support environmentally friendly farming practices, among which agri-environmental-climate measures and organic farming are the key measures interventions addressing focus area 5D. Conversion of arable land to agroforestry, afforestation and forest management are the key measures addressing focus area 5E. ² LSU—livestock standard unit. ³ Calibration—All the conditions and the outcome are transformed into binary values using the percentile thresholds reported in the column headings, associated to the real values provided inside the table.

Variations in the land market are only represented by the change in the average selling price of agricultural land between 2014 and 2022 (from which we derive the LANDPRICE condition). Land prices are supposed to reflect the dynamics of the land market but are often a barrier to entry for small farmers (see Section 1 for more details).

Finally, policy interventions are included here in the form of the CAP financial resources for 2014–2022 for income support (from which we derive the BASIC condition) and coupled payments (from which we derive the FUNDVCS condition) and the percentage of agricultural and forest land under management contracts contributing to focus area 5E (from which we derive the LANDCSQ condition) and focus area 5D (from which we derive the LANDGHG condition), which are expected to influence farming practices in different

ways. The conditions reflecting policy interventions and land prices occur when the value of their reference indicators is higher than the EU average.

Considering the relevance of the income support, in terms of share of the total CAP funds and its alleged influence on the land market, we considered an additional binary variable, the single area payment scheme (from which the condition SAPS), which allows one to distinguish between MS where income support is distributed to farmers through a limited number of entitlements (non-occurrence of SAPS) and those where income support is proportional to the UAA (occurrence of SAPS). The latter system has been shown to have a higher influence on land prices [21]. Focus areas 5D and 5E encompass the policy instruments addressing climate objectives in the MSs' rural development programs (RDP) for the programming period 2014–2022. Within these policy instruments, focus area 5D includes most of the RDP agri-environmental-climate measures aimed at reducing the use of inputs (e.g., conservation agriculture, organic farming), while focus area 5E mainly includes measures aimed at adapting to climate change and mitigating climate change (e.g., conversion of arable land to pasture and meadow, afforestation, pasture and forest management).

The thresholds shown in Table 1 have been defined according to a calibration procedure intended to minimize skewness (achieving a balanced distribution of observations between presence/absence of a condition) and to ensure robustness (no appreciable change in the results when the thresholds for individual conditions are slightly changed) for the conditions addressing policy interventions and land prices. The thresholds of the outcome and of the changes in structural conditions are set equal to zero to separate positive and negative variations. No calibration is needed for the SAPS condition, which is binary (see Annex A for further details).

Table 2 provides the directional expectation of the set of conditions for the GHG outcome. For instance, it is assumed that any increase in GHG emissions is primarily influenced by the physical growth of the agricultural sector (i.e., increase in the UAA and in the LSU) and, to a lower extent, by (i) the lack of incentives influencing the adoption of sustainable practices, which in turn affects the quality of the physical growth; (ii) the presence of perverse incentives, such as the coupled income support, which incentivizes the concentration of the agricultural areas and livestock in the most productive regions [22], and (iii) the income support, which cause the rise of land prices, thus limiting access to land for small farmers and favoring the transfer of land from small to large farms [23].

Table 2. Directional expectations for the GHG outcome.

Description of the Expectations	Logical Reminders Not Used to Simplify the Solution
The growth of the agricultural sector positively influences GHG emissions	~LAND*~LVK
Beneficial incentives addressing farming practices negatively influence GHG emissions	LANDCSQ*LANDGHG
The SAPS coupled with a high level of basic payment leads to an increase in land prices, limiting access to land for small holders and favoring land concentration, which has a positive influence on GHG emissions	~LANDPRICE*~BASIC*~SAPS *~LANDSP*~LVKSP
The coupled support favors the intensification of farming systems, which has a positive influence on GHG emissions	~FUNDEVCS

Notes: ~, negated outcome; *, set intersection.

The inclusion of directional expectations in the analysis allows the identification of an intermediate solution, which is more complex than the parsimonious solution, but which allows the discrimination of cases that displays conditions consistent and inconsistent with expectations.

3. Results and Discussion

Following the QCA procedure described above, we checked the existence of necessary and sufficient conditions for both the outcome and its absence. Necessary conditions only exist for the GHG outcome (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Analysis of necessity. Notes: ~, negated condition; +, set union. Performance indicators: Consistency—Presence of cases showing opposite outcomes; Coverage—Presence of cases not explained by the relation; Relevance of Necessity—Presence of the negated outcome when the condition is absent. Range of performance indicators: 0 (low performance)–1 (high performance). Cases situated below the diagonal are consistent. Cases in the upper left quadrant are deviant for consistency; cases in the lower left quadrant are influencing the coverage trivialness. Performance thresholds: Consistency, 0.900 (required); Coverage, 0.600; Relevance of necessity, 0.500.

The existence of complex necessary conditions (combination of conditions) for the GHG outcome implies that more reasons can explain the increase in GHG emissions from agriculture for some MSs over the period analyzed here (2014–2022). Namely, the absence of land under management contracts to reduce emissions or increase carbon sequestration, \sim LANDCSQ + \sim LANDGHG, is necessary for the GHG outcome to occur (dots in the upper right quadrant of Figure 2). However, the same condition also holds for some MSs that show a reduction in GHG emissions (dots in the lower right quadrant of Figure 2). This explains why the condition \sim LANDCSQ + \sim LANDGHG is necessary for the GHG outcome to occur, since no increase in emissions is found when this condition is absent (with the sole exception of RO, a deviant case of consistency in kind, shown in the upper left quadrant of Figure 2).

Conversely, the absence of necessary conditions characterizes the negated outcome, meaning that there are no necessary conditions supporting the reduction in GHG emissions (\sim GHG), at least with respect to the variables analyzed here⁶.

Note that the analysis of necessity involves the whole set of observations, since it requires the presence of the condition if the outcome is present, whereas the analysis of

sufficiency can involve only part of the set of observations since it requires the presence of the outcome if the condition is present but the outcome can occur even in the absence of the condition (i.e., other conditions can explain the outcome). Thus, the analysis of sufficiency complements the analysis of necessity by allowing the clustering of observations for different combinations of conditions that are found to be sufficient for the outcome to occur.

Table 3 shows the results of the analysis of sufficiency for both GHG and its absence. Without loss of generality, we only provide the intermediate solution following the procedure described above, avoiding the inclusion of logical reminders that are inconsistent with the necessary conditions and with our expectations in the minimization procedure.

Table 3. Analysis of sufficiency. Raw performance scores of the intermediate solution.

Outcome	Conditions	Consistency	PRI	Raw Coverage	Unique Coverage	Cases
GHG	~SAPS*~LANDGHG*~LAND	0.932	0.912	0.327	0.041	SL; HR; LU; DK; FI; MT
	BASIC*LVKSP*LANDPRICE	0.962	0.951	0.240	0.088	LU; DK; AT; IE
	~LANDGHG*LANDCSQ*LVKSP	0.884	0.821	0.260	0.027	PT; DK; MT; CY; LV
	FUNDVCS*~BASIC*~LANDCSQ	0.955	0.939	0.315	0.014	FI; SE; BG; PL
	Solution formula	0.930	0.913	0.677		
~GHG	~SAPS*LANDGHG*LANDCSQ	0.819	0.699	0.354	0.020	IT; DE; UK; BE
	BASIC*LANDGHG*~LANDPRICE	0.623	0.408	0.203	0.009	DE; EE
	FUNDVCS*~BASIC*LANDCSQ*LAND	0.805	0.609	0.381	0.000	FR; BE; LT
	Solution formula	0.757	0.611	0.636		

Notes: ~, negated outcome; *, set intersection. Cases separated by semicolons belong to different truth table rows. Performance indicators: Consistency—Presence of cases showing opposite outcomes; Proportional reduction in inconsistency (PRI)—Presence of cases showing opposite outcomes (additional to consistency); Coverage—Presence of cases not explained by the relation. Range of performance indicators: 0 (low performance)–1 (high performance). Performance thresholds: Consistency, 0.750; PRI, 0.600.

The information provided in Table 3 is complemented by the information provided in Figure 3, which shows the cases that are not covered by the analysis of sufficiency (upper-left quadrant of Figure 3A,B) and the cases contradicting the statement of sufficiency (lower-right quadrant of Figure 3A,B). For both the GHG outcome and its absence, there are no deviant cases (absence of observations in the lower-right quadrant of Figure 3A,B), but the coverage is not perfect (presence of observations in the upper-left quadrant of Figure 3A,B). The lack of coverage is especially evident for the negated outcome, meaning that some cases are not captured by the analysis, suggesting that for these cases other conditions than those analyzed here can explain the reduction in emissions during the observation period.

The following equations can be deduced from the above analysis for both the outcome and its absence:

$$\sim \text{LANDGHG} * [\sim \text{SAPS} * \sim \text{LAND} + \text{LANDCSQ} * \text{LVKSP} + \text{LANDCSQ} * \text{BASIC} * \text{LVKSP} * \text{LANDPRICE}] + \sim \text{LANDCSQ} * [\text{FUNDVCS} * \sim \text{BASIC} + \text{LANDGHG} * \text{BASIC} * \text{LVKSP} * \text{LANDPRICE}] \iff \text{GHG} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{LANDGHG} * [\sim \text{SAPS} * \text{LANDCSQ} + \text{BASIC} * \sim \text{LANDPRICE}] + \text{FUNDVCS} * \sim \text{BASIC} * \text{LANDCSQ} * \text{LAND} \implies \sim \text{GHG} \tag{2}$$

The conditions provided in Equation (1) are found to be necessary and sufficient for the GHG outcome to occur. Necessity is determined by ~LANDGHG + ~LANDCSQ, meaning that the outcome cannot occur in the absence of this condition, while sufficiency is determined by the combination of conditions in brackets, meaning that the presence of these conditions reveals the presence of the outcome.

Figure 3. Analysis of sufficiency. Intermediate solutions for the outcome (GHG, graph A) and its absence (~GHG, graph B). Notes: Cases situated above the diagonal are consistent. In the upper-left quadrant are deviant cases for coverage; in the lower-right quadrant are deviant cases consistent in kind. Performance thresholds: Consistency, 0.750; PRI, 0.600.

Not surprisingly, Table 3 shows that the low share of agricultural land under CAP management contracts for 2014–2022 aimed at reducing emissions or at improving carbon sequestration helps to explain the actual increase in GHG emissions in most MSs. In any case, the combination of \sim LANDGHG and \sim LANDCSQ turns out to be a necessary but insufficient condition to explain the observed increase in GHG emissions. In fact, the analysis of sufficiency provides additional details that help to further disentangle the causes of the increase in GHG emissions.

Apparently, the increase in GHG emissions from agriculture, which occurred in some MSs (SL and HR; LU and DK; FI; MT) over the study period, is associated with the reduction in agricultural land under management contracts for climate change mitigation and the reduction in agricultural land (mix of conditions \sim SAPS* \sim LANDGHG* \sim LAND, Table 3). The simple argument for this unexpected combination of conditions is that the increase in emissions associated with the low share of agricultural land under management contracts for climate change mitigation more than offsets the reduction in emissions associated with the loss of agricultural land. The latter, in turn, is mainly associated with urban sprawl [33–36] and, to a minor extent, with land abandonment [16]. However, to the best of our knowledge, this has not yet been sufficiently explored by researchers and remains an issue to be further investigated, given the relevance of this phenomenon revealed by this study.

For another group of MSs (LU and DK; AT; IE), the increase in GHG emissions is associated with the combined effect of the increase in land prices, the high level of basic payments and the increase in the concentration of livestock farms (mix of conditions BASIC*LVKSP*LANDPRICE, Table 3). Such a combination of conditions supports our expectations described in Section 2, which, in turn, are based on the theoretical insights of [21] and the evidence addressed by [37] in Europe and, most recently, by [38] in China. Namely, there is some evidence that income support payments influence the land market, with the value of the land increasing with the level of the payments. The increase in the value of the agricultural land hampers access to land by small farmers, thereby accelerating the process of concentration of both land and livestock. Finally, the process of concentration appears to be accompanied by the intensification of farming systems, with associated environmental consequences [39,40].

However, the concentration of livestock farms seems to trigger an increase in GHG emissions from agriculture, even if this is associated with a low effort to mitigate climate change and to a high effort to increase carbon sequestration (mix of conditions LVKSP* \sim LANDGHG*LANDCSQ, Table 3). This relationship is found for a heterogeneous group of MSs (MT and CY, PT, DK, LV). At first sight, this relationship seems contradictory. Nevertheless, the increase in carbon sequestration practices in agriculture is not necessarily associated with a reduction in GHG emissions. For example, trade-offs have been documented for tillage management [41], crop rotations [42] and especially for the application of organic fertilizers [3]. This suggests that the concentration of livestock production poses the problem of animal waste disposal. The sustainable management of animal waste is, in fact, carbon sequestration measures accompanying the need to mitigate the negative impacts brought about by livestock concentration.

For a final group of MSs (FI and SE; BG; PL), the increase in GHG emissions is associated with the combined effect of the reduction in the land under management contracts for carbon sequestration practices, the high share of funds for coupled payments and the low level of the basic payment (mix of conditions FUNDVCS* \sim BASIC* \sim LANDCSQ, Table 3). There is some evidence that coupled payments encourage the intensification of farming systems (i.e., it indirectly incentivizes the use of inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides [22]). However, the intensification process triggered by this measure can be partially offset by other instruments aimed to promote sustainable farming practices.

With respect to the conditions related to the reduction of GHG emissions, the performance scores show less consistent relationships compared to the conditions related to the increase in GHG emissions, which is reflected in the strength of the relationships

between conditions and outcomes that can be considered sufficient but not necessary (see Equations (1) and (2)). This indicates that the phenomenon in question is not fully explained by the conditions analyzed in the present study. It appears that the reduction in GHG emissions is associated with a combination of a high proportion of agricultural land under management contracts covering both climate change mitigation and carbon sequestration efforts and the application of direct area-based income SAPS support schemes for a group of MSs (IT; UK; DE and BE), which was found to have no impact on land prices (mx of conditions \sim SAPS * LANDGHG * LANDCSQ, Table 3) [21].

For other MSs, the reduction in GHG emissions is associated with a high proportion of agricultural land under management contracts for climate change mitigation (DE; EE) and a high proportion of agricultural land under management contracts for carbon sequestration (FR; BE; LT), which may offset the possible perverse effects of basic payments on land prices and coupled payments on the intensification of farming systems.

Among the MSs not included in our analysis, it is worth mentioning Spain (ES), where the reduction in GHG emissions is attributed to the ambitious afforestation program financed and implemented during the study period [43]. This seems to compensate for the lack of other subsidies aimed at sustainable agriculture and the increasing concentration of livestock farms. In addition to that, the conditions explored in our paper did not contribute well to explaining the reduction in emissions recorded for Greece (EL) for the period of investigation, for which only necessary conditions were found. The agricultural sector of EL faced important changes in recent years [44] but not in the period of investigation, suggesting that the recorded reduction in emissions can be attributed mainly to a further extensification of the cultivated land accompanied with important public subsidies. Among the MSs not included in our analysis, it is finally worth mentioning RO, where increased GHG emissions can be attributed to the important deforestation that the country is facing in some areas [45].

4. Conclusions

By and large, the analysis conducted in this study provides straightforward explanations for the increase in GHG emissions observed in certain member states from agriculture during the 2014–2022 CAP programming period. Less obvious are the causes that might explain the reduction in emissions observed in other member states.

In general, the increase in GHG emissions from agriculture is driven by the presence of perverse incentives and the absence of desired incentives. Perverse incentives (e.g., income support payments and voluntary coupled payments) are incentives that have unintended/unwanted consequences (e.g., favoring the concentration and intensification of farming systems). An example of desired incentives are funds to promote climate change mitigation and carbon sequestration practices.

On the other hand, the reduction in GHG emissions from agriculture is associated with the existence of a mix of desired incentives, sometimes capable of offsetting the perverse effects of other policy instruments. A linkage between policy instruments and environmental impacts is particularly apparent for those member states that use a coherent mix of policy instruments, i.e., mainly aimed at increasing farmers' income (BG, PL, FI and SE) or at improving sustainable management (IT, DE, UK, EE and LT). However, there are also cases where perverse incentives can hinder the impact of desired incentives (PT, DK, LT, CY and MT) and vice versa (FR, BE, LT). In addition, emissions were found to increase mainly in eastern and northern European MSs (BG, PL, CZ, HR, SL, LV, FI, SE) and to decrease in central and southern MSs (FR, DE, IT, ES). However, it is worth noting that not all countries are equally responsible in their commitment to reduce emissions. This is reflected in the different environmental commitments that each EU MS must fulfill in order to comply with international climate agreements, which are addressed in the Effort Sharing Regulation (EU) 2018/842.

In any case, the analysis so far shows the lack of a comprehensive and coherent policy framework to ensure more sustainable agriculture in the EU. The lack of a common vision,

which is partly reflected in the different ways in which MSs design policy instruments and finance their agriculture may contribute to limiting the EU's ability to meet future environmental and climate change objectives.

The study presented in this paper is not completely exhaustive in addressing how the CAP has contributed to influencing the environmental impacts of the agricultural sector. This is mainly because we did not examine how member states designed their policy instruments, which are often only similar in appearance, as commitments for the same instruments may differ significantly between member states [46]. Furthermore, the analysis carried out in this study provides only qualitative information, showing the existence of a relationship between conditions and outcomes, but not quantifying the influence of conditions on outcomes.

Most importantly, the results obtained through this formalized QCA analysis do not "prove" causal relations. Rather, it reveals patterns of associations across sets of observations, thereby providing support for the existence of such causal relations. Hence, whether it makes sense (or not) to interpret such associations as causal relations depends on the insights derived from within-case analyses provided in the discussion, as well as on existing empirical and theoretical knowledge of the phenomenon under investigation, provided in Section 1.

In addition, the limited number of observations available for the study and the lack of information and policy evaluations at a local level allows detecting only very general causalities. Nevertheless, the causal relationships explored in this study are likely to persist in the 2023–2027 CAP programming period, as the same incentives will continue to be used, albeit with some variations (e.g., the introduction of agri-environmental schemes and crop rotation conditionality).

Overall, further research is needed to understand the circumstances that have led some of CAP incentives to have perverse effects and to explore how best to combine incentives to pursue different objectives, thereby minimizing possible trade-offs and contributing to the development of coherent future agricultural policies in the EU.

Author Contributions: F.G. conceived and wrote the manuscript. F.V. and I.C. revised and improved the original version. G.D.G. administered the project, revised the manuscript and supervised the activity. A.M., M.V.L., I.F. and D.M. contributed conceiving the original version and revising the manuscript. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by the European Joint Program for SOIL "Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils" (EJP SOIL), grant number 862695.

Data Availability Statement: Data are available on request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Appendix A

In the present paper, we partially rely on the enhanced standard analysis procedure developed by [30] to handle logical reminders. This approach allows one to avoid the use of incoherent logical reminders: logical reminders contradicting the statement of necessity, logical reminders contradicting expectations and logical reminders contradicting simplifying assumptions. The first element of incoherence implies avoiding the inclusion of the negated necessary conditions on the logical reminders used to simplify the solution, since the presence of a necessary condition requires that the outcome cannot be observed in its absence. The second element of incoherence implies avoiding the use of logical reminders contradicting the underlying directional expectations for the minimization of the outcome. The third element of incoherence implies avoiding the use of the same reminders for the logical minimization of the outcome and its absence for the analysis of sufficiency, since sufficiency implies that a condition cannot be observed for both the outcome and the negated outcome. We consider this last element of the enhanced standard analysis arguable, since logical reminders are unobserved combinations of conditions whose exclusive role

is to simplify the solution, allowing common combinations to be identified among the observations considered in the analysis. Indeed, simplifying the solution means excluding conditions for which relationships cannot be determined, either because they are irrelevant or (most probably) because there are not enough observations to capture their influence. For the same reason, it does not make sense to initially limit the number of conditions based on the number of observations. Rather, one must start from a deep knowledge of the problem and use the conditions that can explain the phenomenon under investigation, irrespective of the number of observations under analysis. Variables excluded from the intermediate solution should not be considered as uninfluential in a broad sense, but as not explicative for the group of observations studied.

Appendix B

Figure A1 provides information about the calibration on the variables listed in Table 1. Calibration is a fundamental operation in qualitative comparative analysis. It is a transformational process from the raw numerical data to set membership scores, based on a certain number of qualitative anchors or thresholds. The choice of the calibration thresholds should be theoretically informed and must be justified, as it influences the results of the analysis.

Figure A1. Calibration of the outcome and conditions. Note: On the y-axis we report the fuzzy scores used for the analysis and on the x-axis the raw scores drawn from official data. The dotted lines are alternative thresholds used to check for robustness. The threshold was set at 0 for both the outcome and the structural conditions addressing a variation for the period of investigation, while median values were used to define thresholds for policy conditions and 0.5 for the binary SAPS condition. A certain arbitrariness can be identified in the selection of median values for policy conditions. For these conditions we performed a robustness check consisting of running the same QCA procedure described in the main text but using alternative calibration thresholds. The outcome of the robustness check did not contradict the original one, but it was found to be less robust, considering the higher skewness associated with the alternative calibration thresholds.

Notes

- 1 For instance, the recent biofuel-driven growth of monoculture in the United States caused a decrease in the presence of natural enemies to soybean fields by 24% with a consequent increase in pesticide use [6]. For similar reasons, again in the United States, the recent epidemic of southern corn leaf blight in maize monoculture resulted in a 15% crop loss [7]. A study conducted in China revealed that rice varieties planted in mixtures significantly reduce the incidence of blast diseases, increasing crop yield [8]. Another study conducted recently in the EU revealed that increasing plant species diversity significantly reduces the incidence of pest diseases in grasslands [9].
- 2 The national inventories of anthropogenic emissions by sources and removals by sinks are reported annually by MSs under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Reg. EU 525/2013. They also provide a reference for monitoring the achievement of GHG emission reduction targets at national and European levels as set out in the Effort Sharing Regulation (Reg. EU 2018/842 as amended by Reg. EU 2023/857) for the reduction of GHG emissions by 2030, and the recent European Climate Law (Reg. EU 2021/1119) for the overall target of net zero GHG emissions by 2050.
- 3 It is estimated that almost 50% of the total GHG emissions in the agricultural sector stem from livestock, with methane (CH₄) released from enteric fermentation. Emissions of nitrous oxide (N₂O) from soil, associated with fertilizer application (31%) and the management of manure (16%), are also significant in the primary sector [13].
- 4 From its inception in 1957, until 1992, the CAP has adopted sectorial price policies that encourage farmers to increase their production, resulting in a shift from deficiency to excessive production for many categories of agricultural products. Consequently, the EU had to bear high costs to support prices in order to defend farmers' incomes and dispose of surpluses.
- 5 This refers to priority 5 (specifically to focus area 5D and focus area 5E) as defined in Article 5 of EU Regulation 1305/2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).
- 6 Other conditions not included in the analysis presented in this study, such as afforestation, changes in land use from arable land to permanent crops, changes in livestock management (e.g., transition from intensive to extensive livestock systems), can significantly contribute to influencing changes in GHG emissions from agriculture. Such aspects are partially captured by the agri-environmental-climate measures of the CAP analyzed in this study. To avoid the risk of using redundant information, we limited the analysis to the set of variables more directly related to the hypothesis of our study.

References

1. Leahy, S.; Clark, H.; Reisinger, A. Challenges and Prospects for Agricultural Greenhouse Gas Mitigation Pathways Consistent with the Paris Agreement. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **2020**, *4*, 69. [CrossRef]
2. Poore, J.; Nemecek, T. Reducing Food's Environmental Impacts through Producers and Consumers. *Science* **2018**, *360*, 987–992. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
3. Springmann, M.; Clark, M.; Mason-D'Croz, D.; Wiebe, K.; Bodirsky, B.L.; Lassaletta, L.; de Vries, W.; Vermeulen, S.J.; Herrero, M.; Carlson, K.M.; et al. Options for Keeping the Food System within Environmental Limits. *Nature* **2018**, *562*, 519–525. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
4. Buckwell, A.; Elisabet, N. *What Is the Safe Operating Space for EU Livestock*; RISE Foundation: Brussels, Belgium, 2018; pp. 1–108.
5. Trębicki, P.; Finlay, K. Pests and Diseases under Climate Change; Its Threat to Food Security. In *Food Security and Climate Change*; Wiley: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2019; pp. 229–249.
6. Landis, D.A.; Gardiner, M.M.; van der Werf, W.; Swinton, S.M. Increasing corn for biofuel production reduces biocontrol services in agricultural landscapes. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **2008**, *105*, 20552–20557. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
7. Heinemann, J.A.; Massaro, M.; Coray, D.S.; Agapito-Tenfen, S.Z.; Wen, J.D. Sustainability and innovation in staple crop production in the US Midwest. *Int. J. Agric. Sustain.* **2014**, *12*, 71–88. [CrossRef]
8. Zhu, Y.; Chen, H.; Fan, J.; Wang, Y.; Li, Y.; Chen, J.; Fan, J.; Yang, S.; Hu, L.; Leung, H. Genetic diversity and disease control in rice. *Nature* **2000**, *406*, 718–722. [CrossRef]
9. Rottstock, T.; Joshi, J.; Kummer, V.; Fischer, M. Higher plant diversity promotes higher diversity of fungal pathogens, while it decreases pathogen infection per plant. *Ecology* **2014**, *95*, 1907–1917. [CrossRef]
10. Ukhurebor, K.E.; Aigbe, U.O.; Olayinka, A.S.; Nwankwo, W.; Emegha, J.O. Climatic Change and Pesticides Usage: A Brief Review of Their Implicative Relationship. *Assumpt. Univ. EJournal Interdiscip. Res.* **2020**, *5*, 44–49.
11. Sokos, C.K.; Mamolos, A.P.; Kalburttji, K.L.; Birtsas, P.K. Farming and Wildlife in Mediterranean Agroecosystems. *J. Nat. Conserv.* **2013**, *21*, 81–92. [CrossRef]
12. Ciaian, P.; Kancs, D.; Swinnen, J. The Impact of the 2013 Reform of the Common Agricultural Policy on Land Capitalization in the European Union. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* **2013**, *36*, 643–673. [CrossRef]
13. European Environment Agency. EEA Greenhouse Gases—Data Viewer. 2023. Available online: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/data-viewers/greenhouse-gases-viewer> (accessed on 28 August 2023).
14. European Environment Agency. *Trends and Projections in Europe 2023*; EEA Report 07/2023; European Environment Agency: Copenhagen, Denmark, 2023. Available online: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/trends-and-projections-in-europe-2023> (accessed on 28 October 2023).

15. Mbow, H.-O.P.; Reisinger, A.; Canadell, J.; O'Brien, P. *Special Report on Climate Change, Desertification, Land Degradation, Sustainable Land Management, Food Security, and Greenhouse Gas Fluxes in Terrestrial Ecosystems (SR2)*; IPCC 650; IPCC: Geneva, Switzerland, 2017.
16. European Court of Auditors. Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and Climate. Special Report 16/2021. 2021. Available online: <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/eca/special-reports/cap-and-climate-16-2021/en/> (accessed on 18 July 2023).
17. Pe'er, G.; Bonn, A.; Bruelheide, H.; Dieker, P.; Eisenhauer, N.; Feindt, P.H.; Hagedorn, G.; Hansjürgens, B.; Herzon, I.; Lomba, Â.; et al. Action Needed for the EU Common Agricultural Policy to Address Sustainability Challenges. *People Nat.* **2020**, *2*, 305–316. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
18. Stainforth, T.; Bowyer, C. *Climate and Soil Policy Brief: Better Integrating Soil into EU Climate Policy*; Institute for European Environmental Policy: Brussels, Belgium, 2020.
19. Frascarelli, A. L'evoluzione Della Pac e Le Imprese Agricole: Sessant'anni Di Adattamento. *Agriregionieuropa* **2017**, *13*, 1–7.
20. Galioto, F.; Musotti, F. The Governance of Agricultural Lands in Marginal Areas: A Conceptual Framework. *Ecol. Econ.* **2023**, *212*, 107933. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Ciaian, P.; Baldoni, E.; Kancs, d.; Drabik, D. The Capitalization of Agricultural Subsidies into Land Prices. *Annu. Rev. Resour. Econ.* **2021**, *13*, 17–38. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Gohin, A. Assessing CAP Reform: Sensitivity of Modelling Decoupled Policies. *J. Agric. Econ.* **2006**, *57*, 415–440. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Nyéléni Europe and Central Asia. *Roots of Resilience: Land Policy for an Agroecological Transition in Europe*; Nyéléni Europe and Central Asia: Brussels, Belgium, 2021.
24. Spinelli, L.; Roberto, F. L'evoluzione Delle Aziende Agricole Italiane Attraverso Cinquant'anni Di Censimenti (1961–2010). *Agriregionieuropa* **2012**, *8*, 6.
25. Harvey, F. Fewer, Bigger, More Intensive: EU Vows to Stem Drastic Loss of Small Farms. *The Guardian*, 21 May 2021; 4.
26. Michalek, J.; Ciaian, P.; Kancs, d. Capitalization of the Single Payment Scheme into Land Value: Generalized Propensity Score Evidence from the European Union. *Land Econ.* **2014**, *90*, 260–289. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Wagemann, C.; Schneider, C.Q. Notions and Operations in Set Theory. In *Set-Theoretic Methods for the Social Sciences: A Guide to Qualitative Comparative Analysis*; Cambridge University Press: New York, NY, USA, 2012; pp. 42–56.
28. Ragin, C.C. *The Comparative Method: Moving beyond Qualitative and Quantitative Strategies*; University of California Press: Berkeley, CA, USA, 1987.
29. Aarebrot, F.H.; Bakka, P.H. Die Vergleichende Methode in Der Politikwissenschaft. In *Vergleichende Politikwissenschaft*; Springer: Wiesbaden, Germany, 2003; pp. 57–76.
30. Schneider, C.Q.; Wagemann, C. Doing Justice to Logical Remainders in QCA: Moving beyond the Standard Analysis. *Political Res. Q.* **2013**, *66*, 211.
31. Ragin, C.C. Qualitative Comparative Analysis Using Fuzzy Sets (FsQCA). In *Configurational Comparative Methods*; Sage: Newcastle upon Tyne, UK, 2009; pp. 87–121.
32. Dusa, A. *QCA with R: A Comprehensive Resource*; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2018.
33. Abu Hatab, A.; Cavinato, M.E.R.; Lindemer, A.; Lagerkvist, C.-J. Urban Sprawl, Food Security and Agricultural Systems in Developing Countries: A Systematic Review of the Literature. *Cities* **2019**, *94*, 129–142. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Gumma, M.K.; Mohammad, I.; Nedumaran, S.; Whitbread, A.; Lagerkvist, C.J. Urban Sprawl and Adverse Impacts on Agricultural Land: A Case Study on Hyderabad, India. *Remote Sens.* **2017**, *9*, 1136. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Jiang, L.; Deng, X.; Seto, K.C. The Impact of Urban Expansion on Agricultural Land Use Intensity in China. *Land Use Policy* **2013**, *35*, 33–39. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Meyer, M.A.; Früh-Müller, A. Patterns and Drivers of Recent Agricultural Land-Use Change in Southern Germany. *Land Use Policy* **2020**, *99*, 104959. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Pe'er, G.; Dicks, L.V.; Visconti, P.; Arlettaz, R.; Baldi, A.; Benton, T.G.; Collins, S.; Dieterich, M.; Gregory, R.D.; Hartig, F.; et al. EU Agricultural Reform Fails on Biodiversity. *Science* **2014**, *344*, 1090–1092. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
38. Lin, W.; Huang, J. Impacts of Agricultural Incentive Policies on Land Rental Prices: New Evidence from China. *Food Policy* **2021**, *104*, 102125. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. EEA. Loss of HNV Farmland Due to Agricultural Intensification per NUTS3. European Environmental Agency, 2023. Available online: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/loss-of-hnv-farmland-due-1> (accessed on 16 March 2023).
40. Schreinemachers, P.; Tipraqsa, P. Agricultural Pesticides and Land Use Intensification in High, Middle and Low Income Countries. *Food Policy* **2012**, *37*, 616–626. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Bhattacharyya, S.S.; Leite, F.F.G.D.; France, C.L.; Adekoya, A.O.; Ros, G.H.; de Vries, W.; Melchor-Martínez, E.M.; Iqbal, H.M.; Parra-Saldívar, R. Soil Carbon Sequestration, Greenhouse Gas Emissions, and Water Pollution under Different Tillage Practices. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2022**, *826*, 154161. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Gu, J.; Yuan, M.; Liu, J.; Hao, Y.; Zhou, Y.; Qu, D.; Yang, X. Trade-off between Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration and Nitrous Oxide Emissions from Winter Wheat-Summer Maize Rotations: Implications of a 25-Year Fertilization Experiment in Northwestern China. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2017**, *595*, 371–379. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Vadell, E.; de-Miguel, S.; Pemán, J. Large-Scale Reforestation and Afforestation Policy in Spain: A Historical Review of Its Underlying Ecological, Socioeconomic and Political Dynamics. *Land Use Policy* **2016**, *55*, 37–48. [[CrossRef](#)]

44. Dimopoulos, T.; Helfenstein, J.; Kreuzer, A.; Mohr, F.; Sentas, S.; Giannelis, R.; Kizos, T. Different responses to mega-trends in less favorable farming systems. Continuation and abandonment of farming land on the islands of Lesbos and Lemnos, Greece. *Land Use Policy* **2023**, *124*, 106435. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Petrișor, A.I. Using CORINE data to look at deforestation in Romania: Distribution & possible consequences. *Urbanism. Arhit. Construcții* **2015**, *6*, 83–90.
46. Galioto, F.; Nino, P. Investigating the Reasons behind the Choice to Promote Crop Diversification Practices through the New CAP Reform in Europe. *Land Use Policy* **2023**, *133*, 106861. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.